

GUIDING PRINCIPLES IN THE STATE OF ISRAEL'S FOREIGN ECONOMIC RELATIONS POLICY

LEVKOVICH Lavan Limor

PhD student at Moldova State University

Shaanan College, Israel

limorllavan@gmail.com

ORCID: 0000-0003-2188-3140

Abstract: *The increasing influence of economic and political changes in the world on international diplomacy poses a unique challenge to Israel. The Israeli-Palestinian conflict is at the center of activity of a growing number of civil society organizations from a variety of fields, such as human rights and international law. At the same time, Israel benefits from the unique influence of the Jewish communities on their countries' governments of, and the most prominent example of this is the United States. This unique situation, fueled by both Israel's challenges and assets, emphasizes the need for the formulation of current guiding principles for Israel's economic foreign relations policy and the way the Ministry of Economy and the Ministry of Foreign Affairs operate in relation to civil and business diplomacy that operates alongside official diplomacy.*

Key words: *Economic Relations Policy; International Diplomacy; Entrepreneurial Country; Civil Economic; Society Organizations.*

PRINCIPII DIRECTIVE ÎN POLITICA DE RELAȚII ECONOMICE EXTERNE A STATULUI ISRAEL

LEVKOVICH Lavan Limor

Doctoranda la Universitatea de Stat din Moldova

Colegiul Shaanan, Israel

limorllavan@gmail.com

ORCID: 0000-0003-2188-3140

Rezumat: *Influența crescândă a schimbărilor economice și politice din lume asupra diplomației internaționale reprezintă o provocare unică pentru Israel. Conflictul israeliano-palestinian se află în centrul activității unui număr tot mai mare de organizații ale societății civile din diverse domenii, precum drepturile omului și dreptul internațional. În același timp, Israelul beneficiază de influența unică a comunităților evreiești asupra guvernelor țărilor lor, iar cel mai proeminent exemplu în acest sens este Statele Unite. Această situație unică, alimentată atât de provocările, cât și de activele Israelului, subliniază necesitatea formulării principiilor directe actuale pentru politica de relații*

economice externe a Israelului și modul în care Ministerul Economiei și Ministerul Afacerilor Externe operează în relație cu diplomația civilă și de afaceri care operează alături de diplomația oficială.

Cuvinte cheie: politica de relații economice; diplomație internațională; țara antreprenorială; economia civilă; organizații ale societății.

The increasing influence of economic and political changes in the world on international diplomacy poses a unique challenge to Israel. The Israeli-Palestinian conflict is at the center of activity of a growing number of civil society organizations from a variety of fields, such as human rights and international law. At the same time, Israel benefits from the unique influence of the Jewish communities on their countries' governments of, and the most prominent example of this is the United States. This unique situation, fueled by both Israel's challenges and assets, emphasizes the need for the formulation of current guiding principles for Israel's economic foreign relations policy and the way the Ministry of Economy and the Ministry of Foreign Affairs operate in relation to civil and business diplomacy that operates alongside official diplomacy.

1. **Need for integrative diplomacy** - The Israeli economic and foreign relations system needs to create collaborations between official and professional diplomacy and between a variety of non-state actors, recognize these actors' increasing role in the diplomatic arena, and take part in the process of global civic empowerment. To this end, collaborations must be created with civil economic society organizations, Israeli and multinational business companies, social and business entrepreneurs, diverse communities around the world.

1.1 **Establishing cooperation with Israeli civil society organizations operating abroad** - alongside the continuous activity of the Ministry of Foreign Affairs and official diplomacy, they must develop cooperation with Israeli civil society economic organizations, which maintain regular working relationships with their counterparts abroad and even take part in shaping the global agenda in processes that take place in the UN and other arenas (the field of environmental quality; international trade).

1.2 **Branding Israel as a creative and entrepreneurial country, which strives becoming acquainted with other countries and building trust** - Israel must connect, while creating dialogue and empathy, to issues that are on the world's agenda, such as developing countries, poverty, water, entrepreneurship, agriculture

and food. This will help to brand Israel as a country that is able to offer creative solutions, drive initiatives and inspire. Israeli business companies, and can also promote moves in this direction by emphasizing entrepreneurship, technologies

- 1.3 **Encouraging actions of civil and economic diplomacy** - Israeli civil diplomacy must be promoted by harnessing Israeli civil society organizations and Israeli companies operating abroad. Civil society organizations that maintain working relationships with their counterparts abroad may also serve as important "ambassadors", in particular in light of the fact that many of these organizations are seen abroad as opinion leaders in the national and international space. Such civil economic diplomacy can also contribute to emphasizing the multicultural character of Israeli society, through collaborations with various sectors of Israeli society and with their operation networks abroad.

The integrative diplomacy approach may also have great significance for the unique challenge that Israel faces, in the form of calls for a cultural and economic boycott on the state. Since in many cases the calls for boycott come from civil groups, operating from within civil society and through social activists and community leadership, the establishment of Israeli civil action networks and their operation may provide an effective response to these calls

2. **Involvement in global issues** - Israel must continue to act on global issues where it can contribute and in areas for which it already receives positive evaluation from the international community. Such involvement could even help strengthen society and the economy in Israel. Formulating a clear policy regarding Israel's role in global issues and external communication will leverage the potential of Israel's involvement and the resulting exposure.

- 2.1 **Involvement in the global effort to promote sustainable development** and to address the challenges of poverty, food, agriculture and water, particularly in developing countries - Israel is already involved to some extent in these areas, and a prominent example of this is the resolution that Israel promoted at the UN Assembly regarding "encouraging entrepreneurship, in the private sector and in the public sector, as a preferred way to deal with the challenges of poverty and creating new jobs." Israel leads initiatives in the field of food, agriculture and water technologies, to which investors and international funding

sources can be attracted. The centrality of these issues in the global order is critical.

2.2 Providing aid in international emergency situations - Israel receives positive evaluation in the international community for its rapid mobilization for aid in the face of disaster situations in the world and for its high professional ability in the field. This point invites continued development and regulation to realize the full potential, while examining the cooperation on the subject also with Israeli businesses operating abroad.

2.3 Distribution of unique Israeli knowledge in the field of socio-economic change around the world - action must be taken to promote and dissemination of Israeli models in the field of civil society organizations' activity. This channel of action can be particularly effective in light of the developed activities of Israeli civil society organizations in the fields of education, culture, entrepreneurship and more.

In conclusion, the State of Israel faces diplomatic-economic challenges that focus its actions on the correct choice of communication channels with countries all over the world. There is no doubt that the diplomatic setup has changed, and now the status of governments is reduced compared to previous years. Israel must find the way in which it communicates with countries and especially with the economic-civil bodies that today create an influence on decision makers in the governments of each country.

Bibliography:

1. Ben-Eliezer, U. The Civil Society, the Uncivil Society, and the Difficulty Israel Has Making Peace with the Palestinians, *Journal of Civil Society*, 11:2, 2015. P. 170-186, DOI: [10.1080/17448689.2015.1045697](https://doi.org/10.1080/17448689.2015.1045697)
2. Council Foreign Relation – Government Ministry – 2022. <https://www.cfr.org/>
3. Doron, J. Games in Israeli politics. 2019. Tel Aviv: Ramot (in Hebrew).
4. Harpaz, G. The Role of Dialogue in Reflecting and Constituting International Relations: The Causes and Consequences of a Deficient European-Israeli Dialogue. *Review of International Studies*, 2011, vol. 37, 4, 2019. P. 17 – 22

5. Harpaz, G., Shamis, A. Normative Power Europe and the State of Israel: An Illegitimate EU topia. *Journal of Common Market Studies*, vol. 48, 3, 2017. p. 585- 587.
6. Lerman, A. Diplomacy-in uniform. The magazine "Hashiloh" issue 16, October 2019. pp. 75 - 82. (in Hebrew)
7. Omar H. R. What's behind the relationship between Israel and Arab Gulf states?," *Order From Chaos* (blog), January 28, 2019, www.brookings.edu/blog/order-from-chaos/2019/01/28/whats-behind-the-relationship-between-israel-and-arab-gulf-states/.
8. Richard, Y., Echagues, A. Shrinking Space for Civil Society. The EU Response, Directorate General for External Politics, Policy Department, European Parliament, Brussels, 2017. [http://www.europarl.europa.eu/RegData/etudes/STUD/2017/578039/EXPO_STU\(2017\)578039_EN.pdf](http://www.europarl.europa.eu/RegData/etudes/STUD/2017/578039/EXPO_STU(2017)578039_EN.pdf)
9. The Association for Civil Rights in Israel – 2018. Overview-of-Anti-Democratic-Legislation. <https://law.acri.org.il/en/wp-content/uploads/2018/10/Overview-of-Anti-DemocraticLegislation-October-2018.pdf>
10. The Economist Intelligence Unit (2017). Democracy Index 2017. Free speech under attack. https://pages.eiu.com/rs/753-RIQ-438/images/Democracy_Index_2017.pdf